

Using GPU for hyperspectral image parallel deep learning classification

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Résumé La classification des images hyperspectrales (IHS) est devenu plus difficile avec l'avancement des technologies de télédétection. Dans la littérature, de nombreux chercheurs se sont intéressés à ce processus. Cependant, l'énorme quantité d'informations spatiales et spectrales dans ce types d'images rend le problème difficile à résoudre. Cet article propose un processus parallèle pour relever ce défi. Il examine l'importance d'améliorer l'efficacité et l'adaptabilité des classifications parallèles pour résoudre ce problème. Dans ce contexte, nous choisissons d'adapter la classification des IHS en utilisant le CPU et le GPU. Nous avons évalué la différence d'importance entre ces deux devices selon deux métriques la précision de classification et le temps d'exécution. L'utilisation d'un classifieur 3D CNN montre que l'exécution sur un GPU donne le meilleur résultat en termes de temps d'exécution et de précision.

Mots clés HSI, Parallélisme, CPU, GPU, CNN 3D.

Abstract The classification of hyperspectral images (HSI) becomes more challenging with the advent of remote sensing technology. In the literature, many researchers were interested by this process. However, the huge amount of spatial and spectral information in HSI makes the problem hard to solve. This article proposes a parallel process using GPU. It examines the importance of enhancing efficiency and adaptability of parallel classifications for solving this problem. In this context, we choose to fit the HSI classification using CPU and GPU to focus on the importance difference between execution time and accuracy. The use of 3D CNN classifier shows that the implentation using GPU gives the best result of execution time and accuracy results.

Keywords HSI, Parallelism, CPU, GPU, 3D CNN.

1 Introduction

Due to the advancement of remote sensing, HSI has become one of the most interesting types of images. HSI are used in a variety of applications. In general, HSI are represented by a data cube that includes both spatial and spectral information [9]. This kind of images can be treated in several ways, such as dimension reduction, unmixing and classification.

Remote sensing of earth's surface is the process of detecting and motorizing the physical characteristics of an area by measuring its reflected or emitted radiation remotely [2]. It provides information that is difficult to acquire on the surface. The main limitations of remote sensing are the lack of ground and the specificity of information [3]. The HSI is widely used due to its benefits from the detailed spectral information contained in each pixel and the results available are quite high. The main fields that use HSI are agriculture, medical and criminal investigations [7]. It is considered as a valuable source of information for applications [18]. It is characterized by continuous spectral reflectance curve and hence better material identification. It has high spectral resolution and it moderates spatial one. The most challenges imposed by HSI are a large volume of data due to high spectral resolution, difference in the spectral information of two adjacent bands [20], much of the information in the scene appears redundant in gray level image. Huge data dimension and spectral mixing and how to process the large amount of data produced are also a main constraint [12]. Classification is used to construct a thematic map of hyperspectral data. The thematic map grouping objects is according to criteria. Each pixel of the image is given a class according to its characteristics. The HSI classification has been studied by many researchers using supervised or unsupervised classification methods and different tests, by many researchers, show that traditional classification techniques and methods like SVM, KNN, XGBoost are not very efficient with this kind of images [8]. DL(deep learning) is a class of machine learning methods that can be suitable for many tasks specially in HSI classification. DL models are extremely complex with many parameters in deep-seam structures that typically require days or weeks of training on a CPU (Central Processor unit). In order to maintain acceptable training times, DL Algorithms must be trained on a platform with GPU [16].

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 summarizes the hardware and software parallelism in the literature. Section 3 is reserved for the discussion of the experimental results. Finally, the paper is achieved by a conclusion.

2 Hardware Parallelism

Nowadays, with the development of computer technologies, it is possible to process and analyze the large data of HSI .as in the software side we find cloud, big data,

distribution and parallelism. Thus, on the hardware side, there is an evolution in the performance of CPUs (Multicore), GPUs (NVIDIA), RAM (DDR4, DDR5) and hard drives (SSD, VSD). So, parallelism was been imposed at the level of processor architectures (central or graphic), with multi-core processors as well as at the level of machine architectures with clusters, supercomputers, etc.

2.1 CPU Parallelism

The CPU is the main component of any digital computer system [21]. There are two types of parallelism on the CPU. Sequential parallelism is the first type used to augment the number of instructions per cycle (IPC) in a sequential processing which accelerates the calculation. This parallelism types includes the superscaler processor and the vector pipeline. The second type, there is the CPU parallelism that allows to process more tasks at the same time as multi-core, multiprocessor and multithread [15].

2.2 GPU Parallelism

With ever-larger data size, analyzing HSI requires significant computing resources. The developments carried out in this topic had the effect of reducing this pressure by reducing the time of calculations required to estimate abundance maps. Another way to meet this technical challenge is to use hardware resources more suited to intensive computation. The development of parallel computing tools over the past decade responds to this approach [4].

Different parallelization options, each based on specific hardware architecture, are now available. A different type of parallelization is represented by the GPU model. This does not replace the CPU but is used in addition to the latter. Its structures include several blocks, each consisting of a control unit, a cache memory, and several computing units. Typically, several hundred calculation units are present on a GPU. This assembly exchanges data with a working memory which is dedicated to it, called global memory (shown in Figure 1). Having more compute units than control units makes the GPU more suited to data parallelism.

For parallelism on GPU which is the SIMT (Single Instruction, Multiple Threads) that is a programming model used with GPU. This name comes from two other parallel programming models SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data: Flynn taxonomy architecture) [10]. SIMT is more flexible than SIMD. SIMT is an execution model used in parallel calculation in wich is an SIMD combined with multi-threading. The SIMT execution model has been implemented on several GPUs and is relevant for general purpose computing on graphics processing units (GPGPUs) [6].

Figure 1. CPU and GPU Architecture

According to the Flynn's taxonomy, we will explain the SIMD and the MIMD architecture. SIMD is a type of parallel machine whose processing units can execute a single instruction in various data streams to a given horological cycle. This architecture is used by processor arrays such as pipelines, IPC and vector unit and most modern computers. Moreover, GPUs use this type of architecture [6][17]. The SIMD machine provides a model which is executed model near the vector machine so that it is totally synchronous [15]. On the other hand, MIMD is a type of parallel machine whose processing units can execute different instructions in different data streams at a given clock cycle. This architecture is used by the most up-to-date supercomputers and multicore (multi-threaded) and multiprocessor computers[6][17]. In the MIMD machine, the execution becomes asynchronous and different instructions can be executed simultaneously.

There are three paradigms of hardware architectures:

- Distributed memory [17]: each processor has its own local memory and can access it independently. All computers are connected via a network and can request data from other computers.
- Shared memory [17]: multiple processors can access memory independently, but they share memory in shared. Parallel shared memory architectures can be classified as UMA or NUMA [6].
- Hybrid memory [17]: most modern supercomputers use a type of hybrid memory architecture that combines shared and distributed memory architectures. All processors in a machine can share memory and request data from other computers. This architecture uses specialized coprocessors to accelerate certain types of computing operations such as GPUs, FPGAs [21].

3 Sofetware Parallelism

3.1 NVIDIA CUDA

Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) is a software and hardware architecture for general-purpose computing on graphics processing units (GPGPUs) developed and released by NVIDIA in 2007. This kicks of NVIDIA revolutionary move toward GPGPU and high-performance computing (HPC). Combining tremendous programmability, performance, and ease of use. A typical CUDA program runs in one or more stages, either on the host (CPU) or as a GPU (NVIDIA 2009). CUDA is designed to support heterogeneous computing, where the serial part of the application runs on the CPU and the parallel part runs on the GPU [11].

3.2 OpenCL

Another standard is OpenCL which was developed by Khronos [13]. It is used to write OpenCL kernels [14]. These standards are usually implemented on GPUs from different vendors because they do not depend on GPU hardware [19].

4 Experimentation and results

With ever-larger data size, analyzing HSI requires significant computing resources. The development carried out in this topic has the effect of reducing this pressure by reducing the time of calculations required to estimate classification maps. To meet this challenge, there is a lot of hardware more suited to intensive computation. So, we will use 3D-CNN [5] as a deep learning classifier using CPU and GPU to show the effect of the choice of the hardware.

4.1 Data Set description

To experiment our approach we have used,India Pines data set, which is collected by AVIRIS (the Airborne Visible/ Infrared Imaging Spectrometer) sensor, represents northwestern India [1]. This data set contains 145×145 pixels with a spatial resolution of 20 m per pixel and 220 spectral bands in the wavelength range of 0.4 to 2.5 m. The ground truth contains 16 classes shown in Figure 2.

4.2 Obtained results

All the experiments were performed on an online platform known as Google Colab. Google Colab provides an option to execute the codes on python 3 notebook

Figure 2. India pines dataset

with GPU and have 12.7 GB of RAM. In all the experiments, the initial Test/Train set is divided into a 30/70% ratio on which training samples (70% of the entire population).

For evaluation purposes, Average Accuracy (AA), Overall Accuracy (OA) and Kappa (k) coefficient have been computed from the confusion matrices. AA represents the average class-wise classification performance, OA is computed as the number of correctly classified examples out of the total test examples and finally, is known as a statistical metric that considered the mutual information regarding a strong agreement among classification and ground-truth maps.

For the tests, we used the following methods: CPU and GPU. The proposed approach using GPU has the best results in terms of accuracy or processing time. Table 1 shows the percentage of OA, AA and Kappa for the different methods. It can be observed from the table that the GPU method outperforms the CPU while maintaining the minimum standard deviation. All the models are based on the hierarchical representation of a spectral-spatial 3D CNN which characterized its high accuracy due to its richness of input data and its complexity than 2D CNN.

Metrics	CPU	GPU
OA (%)	96.96	97.82
AA (%)	96.29	96.21
K (%)	96.53	97.52
Time	4 min	41 s

Table 1. Test results

4.3 Discussion

The quality of the classification map shown in Figure 3 proves that the GPU is much better than the CPU. Among GPU implementation, the map generated in the small segment is better. So, according to these results it is confirmed that the use of the GPU and the parallelism are the better methods to solve the problem of large execution time for large volume of hyperspectral data.

Figure 3. Classification Map (a) Using CPU (2) Using GPU

5 Conclusion

With ever-increasing data sizes, processing hyperspectral images requires significant computing resources. The developments cited throughout this paper will have the effect of reducing this pressure by reducing the time of calculations necessary to estimate abundance maps. Thus, the experimentation proves the efficiency of the use of the GPU as a hardware resource more suitable for intensive and hard calculations.

References

1. Akrem Sellami; Ali Ben Abbas; Vincent Barra and Imed Riadh Farah. Fused 3-D spectral-spatial deep neural networks and spectral clustering for hyperspectral image classification.. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 138:594–600, 2020.
2. Alexander F.; H. Goetz; Gregg Vane Jerry E.; Solomon Barrett and N. Rock. Imaging Spectrometry for Earth Remote Sensing. *SCIENCE*, 228(4704):1147–1153, 7 june 1985.
3. Gregg Vane Jerry E. Solomon Barrett N. Rock Alexander F. H. Goetz. Imaging spectrometry for earth remote sensing. *Imaging spectrometry for earth remote sensing. Science*, 228(4704):1147–1153, 7 june 1985.

4. and al Demarchi, Luca. Recursive feature elimination and random forest classification of natura 2000 grasslands in lowland river valleys of poland based on airborne hyperspectral and lidar data fusion. *Remote Sensing*, 2020.
5. Swalpa Kumar Roy; Gopal Krishna; Shiv Ram Dubey and Bidyut B. Chaudhuri. HybridSN: Exploring 3-D-2-D CNN Feature Hierarchy for Hyperspectral Image Classification. *IEEE GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING LETTERS*, 17(2):277–281, FEBRUARY 2020.
6. Hesham El-Rewini and Mostafa Abd-El-Barr. *ADVANCED COMPUTER ARCHITECTURE AND PARALLEL PROCESSING*. A JOHN WILEY SONS, INC PUBLICATION, simultaneously in Canada, 2005.
7. Akin Ozdemir et al. Deep learning applications for hyperspectral imaging: A systematic review. *Journal of the Institute of Electronics and Computer*, (2):39–56, 2020.
8. Li et al. Deep Learning for Hyperspectral Image Classification: An Overview. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 57(9):6690 – 6709, Sept. 2019.
9. Amira Ayadi Mongi Boulehmi Imed Riadh Farah. Proposed architecture for hyperspectral image parallel processing methods based on gpu. *International Congress of Advanced Technology and Engineering (ICOTEN) ,IEEE*,, 2021.
10. MICHAEL J. FLYNN. Some Computer Organizations and Their Effectiveness. *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON COMPUTERS*, vol. c-21(NO 9):948–960, SEPTEMBER 1972.
11. Jayshree Ghorpade and al. Gpgpu processing in cuda architecture. *arXiv preprint arXiv*, 1202(4347), 2012.
12. Amy Lowe; Nicola Harrison and Andrew P French. Hyperspectral image analysis techniques for the detection and classification of the early onset of plant disease and stress. . *Plant Methods*, 2017.
13. Mert Hidayetoğlu and al. At-scale sparse deep neural network inference with efficient gpu implementation. *IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference (HPEC)*. *IEEE*, 2020.
14. M.Gardner Martinez, Gabriel and W.Feng. Cu2cl: A cuda-to-opencl translator for multi-and many-core architectures. *IEEE 17th International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, 2011.
15. Matthieu Ospici. *Modèles de programmation et d'exécution pour les architectures parallèles et hybrides. Applications à des codes de simulation pour la physique*. HAL, Université de Grenoble, 2013.
16. Zhaoning Zhang; Lujia Yin; Yuxing Peng and Dongsheng Li. A quick survey on large scale distributed deep learning systems. *IEEE 24th International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems (ICPADS)*, pages 1052–1056, 2018.
17. Nikolaos Ploskas and Nikolaos Samaras. *GPU Programming in MATLAB*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/fibonacci-number>, doi.org/10.1016/C2015-0-00281-7, 2016.
18. Pedram Ghamisi; Naoto Yokoya; Jun Li Wenzhi; Liao Sicong; Liu Place Javier; Behnood Rasti and Antonio Plaza. Hyperspectral image: Fundamentals and advances. *A Comprehensive Overview of the State of the Art. IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, 5(4):pp.37–78, December 2017.
19. Smola and S. Narayanamurthy. An architecture for parallel topic models. proc. vldb endow. *Proc. VLDB Endow*, 3(2):703–710, Sep. 2010.
20. V. Sowmya K.; P. Soman and M. Hassaballah. Advances in hyperspectral image and signal processing. *Recent Advances in Computer Vision*, pages pp.401–424, janvier 2019.
21. David B. Thomas. A Comparison of CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, and Massively Parallel Processor Arrays for Random Number Generation. *FPGA '09: Proceedings of the ACM/SIGDA international symposium on Field programmable gate arrays*, (63-72):10, 2009.